

Applications of sets and functions by using an open sets

in Fuzzy neutrosophic topological spaces

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Abstract: The definitions provided by the authors of the current study are offered together with a discussion of the recent advances that they have contributed. We begin with an introduction to fn - $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}$, which includes the concepts of closed and open sets. We explore characteristics in fn - $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}$ and fn - $E_{b_{q_N}}(Q_N)$, and provide an idea of obtained results by adding the notion of $FNb_{q_N}OS$ and analyzing a few of their properties in $fnts$. We've researched the contrasts between the derived, exterior, and frontier notions that are provided. We also looked at the ideas of $\langle \mathcal{T}^{b_{q_N}} \rangle C$ -functions and Γ^S -segregated functions and examined and determined the traits.

Keywords: $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}$, $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}$, $E_{b_{q_N}}(Q_N)$, $fnb_{q_N}OS$, derived, exterior, and frontier

1. Introduction

Uncertainties are a major source of real-world difficulties in the fields of business, finance, medicine, engineering, and the behavioural sciences. Using conventional mathematical methods to solve the uncertainties for these data presents challenges. To avoid problems while working with ambiguous data, there exist methods like fuzzy sets, rough sets, fuzzy sets with intuitionistic properties, and vague sets that may be used as mathematical tools. Due to the inadequate parametrization tools, all of these techniques implicitly face difficulties when attempting to solve problems involving inconsistent and indeterminate data. The characteristics of n -closed sets, interior operators, closure operators, and open sets determine how neutrosophic is used in topology. Topologists explored sets next to neutrosophic closed and open sets.

L. A. Zadeh [29] proposed fuzzy sets in 1965 and investigated various aspects of their features, A fuzzy set is a class of elements with an assortment of membership grades. Such a collection is characterised by a membership (or feature) function that assigns a membership grade, ranging from zero to one, to each item. He extended the notions of inclusion, union, intersection, complement, connection, convexity, etc. to these sets and demonstrated various aspects of these notions in relation to fuzzy sets. In particular, a separation theorem for convex fuzzy sets is proved that does not need the fuzzy sets to be disjoint.

Atanassov [14, 15, 16] have created intuitionistic fuzzy sets and looked through numerous outcomes, he presented the concept of the "Generalised Net" and examined its fundamental characteristics along

with a few of its uses in the fields of artificial intelligence, systems theory, health, economics, transportation, and the chemical industry.

He spearheaded most of the applied research in the field of generalised nets and was the driving force behind its theoretical investigation. Many of the operations and interactions he has established over generalised nets have parallels in the theory of regular Petri nets. Nevertheless, there is no counterpart in Petri net theory for the topological and logical operators he has presented. Atanassov's other primary area of study is fuzzy sets, originally established by Zadeh, which he developed further by presenting the concept of "Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets" and investigating the elements that make up its foundation. He is also recognised as a pioneer in the use of intuitionistic fuzzy sets to expert systems, systems theory, decision-making, and other domains.

F.Smarandache [9, 10, 24] examined the idea of using a neutrosophic set as a technique for resolving problems involving persistent, unpredictable, and unreliable data. He also noted the features of the generalisation of intuitionistic fuzzy logic. The study of the nature, origin, and scope of neutralities as well as their interactions with other ideational spectra is done within a branch of neutrosophy called the neutrosophic set. The neutrosophic set is a robust universal formal framework that was introduced lately. However, from a technical point of view, the neutrosophic set has to be specified.

P. Basker and Broumi Said [5, 6, 7] Investigators investigated the idea of $N\psi_{\alpha}^{\# 0}$ and $N\psi_{\alpha}^{\# 1}$ -spaces and neutrosophic functions in neutrosophic topological spaces, and neutrosophic homeomorphisms from which the notion of (β_{pn}) -OS in pythagorean neutrosophic topological spaces

Neutrosophic topological spaces and the resulting neutrosophic set were studied in 2012 by A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi [23]. The concepts of fuzzy neutrosophic topological spaces and fuzzy neutrosophic sets were examined in 2014 by I. Arockiarani and J. Martina Jency [4]. In 2018, Fatimah M. Mohammed, Anas A. Hijab, and Shaymaa F. Matar [8] implemented fuzzy neutrosophic weakly-generalized closed sets in fuzzy neutrosophic topological spaces.

The concept of sharp, weakly neutrosophic closed functions was introduced by Ali Hussein Mahmood Al Obaidi, Qays Hatem Imran, and Murtadha Mohammed Abdulkadhim [1]. Hypersoft topological spaces were employed by Sagvan Y. Musa and Baravan A. Asaad [22] to connect the concepts.

In 2023, the neutrosophic soft generalised b-closed sets in neutrosophic soft topological spaces were created by Alkan Özkan, Leyda Yazgan, and Sandeep Kaur [2], Muthumari G et al. [20] the neutrosophic over topologized graphs' homomorphism and isomorphism were derived, Tomasz Witczak [27], Interior and closure of anti-minimal and anti-biminimal areas in the framework of anti-topology. The authors developed and examined a novel class of neutrosophic open and closed maps in neutrosophic topological spaces. P.Anbarasi Rodrigo et al. [3] and P. Thangaraja et al. [28]. Separation Axioms, Neighbourhood and Continuity were discussed in [21, 25, 26]. A few descriptions of both new and Neutrosophic objects were covered in [11, 12, 13]. An application of neutrosophic theory and computation of neutrosophic were generalized in [17, 18, 19].

This paper's Section 1 lists the definitions cited by the authors as well as recent advances that they have provided. We introduce the concept of FNB_{qN} OS in Section 2 using *fnts*. FNB_{qN} have determined $Fr_{\#b_{qN}}$, $\beta d^{\#b_{qN}}$, $E_{b_{qN}}(Q_N)$ and $E^{FNB_{qN}}(Q_N)$ studied some of their properties by using the above concepts we have derived the applications of *fn*-open and closed sets. In this study, FNS, FNTS, MN and MX stand for *fn*-set, *fn*-Topological Spaces, Minimum and Maximum respectively.

The following are the main novelties of this paper.

- fn -open and closed sets
- $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -point of interior
- fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -border
- fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -frontier
- fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -exterior
- fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -derived
- fn - Γ^S -segregated
- fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -Totally-Continuous

The essential definitions listed below will aid in understanding this research work.

Definition 1.1.[4] A fn -set A on X is defined as A is equal to $\langle \varpi, I_A(\varpi), J_A(\varpi), K_A(\varpi) \rangle$, ϖ belongs to X where I, J, K from X to $[0, 1]$ and $0 \leq \text{sum of } \{I_A(\varpi), J_A(\varpi), K_A(\varpi)\} \leq 3$.

Definition 1.2. [4] A fn -set, A belongs to the subset of a fn -set B (i.e.,) $A \subseteq B \forall \varpi$ if $I_A(\varpi) \leq I_B(\varpi)$
 $J_A(\varpi) \leq J_B(\varpi)$ $K_A(\varpi) \geq K_B(\varpi)$

Definition 1.3. [4] Let X must represent a non-empty set., and $A = \langle \varpi, I_A(\varpi), J_A(\varpi), K_A(\varpi) \rangle$, $B = \langle \varpi, I_B(\varpi), J_B(\varpi), K_B(\varpi) \rangle$ be two fn -set. Then
 Union of A and B is $\langle \varpi, \text{MX of } \{I_A(\varpi), I_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MN of } \{J_A(\varpi), J_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MN of } \{K_A(\varpi), K_B(\varpi)\} \rangle$
 and Intersection of A and B is $\langle \varpi, \text{MN of } \{I_A(\varpi), I_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MN of } \{J_A(\varpi), J_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MX of } \{K_A(\varpi), K_B(\varpi)\} \rangle$.

Definition 1.4. [4] The difference between two fn -set A and B is defined as
 Differ from A to B is $\langle \varpi, \text{MN of } \{I_A(\varpi), K_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MN of } \{J_A(\varpi), 1 - J_B(\varpi)\}, \text{MN of } \{K_A(\varpi), I_B(\varpi)\} \rangle$.

Definition 1.5. [4] A fn -set it is said that A over the universe X equals

- Null or empty fn -set if $0_N = \langle \varpi, 0, 0, 1 \rangle \forall \varpi \in X$.
- Absolute (universe) fn -set if $1_N = \langle \varpi, 1, 1, 0 \rangle \forall \varpi \in X$.

Definition 1.6. [4] A^c represents the complement of a fn -set A , which is defined as $A^c = \langle \varpi, I_{(A^c)}(\varpi), J_{(A^c)}(\varpi), K_{(A^c)}(\varpi) \rangle$, Where $I_{(A^c)}(\varpi) = K_A(\varpi), J_{(A^c)}(\varpi) = 1 - J_A(\varpi), K_{(A^c)}(\varpi) = I_A(\varpi)$.
 Another way to define the complement of a fn -set A is as $A^c = 1_N - A$.

2. Applications of Fuzzy Neutrosophic open and closed sets

Definition 2.1. A fn s, $\mathcal{Q}_N = \langle H, \zeta_{\mathcal{Q}_N}, \eta_{\mathcal{Q}_N}, \theta_{\lambda_N} \rangle$ in a fn ts Γ is to be

- (i) fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -OS ($FNbOS$), $FNi(FNc(\mathcal{Q}_N)) \cup FNc(FNi(\mathcal{Q}_N)) \supseteq \mathcal{Q}_N$
- (ii) fn - $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -CS ($FNbCS$), $FNi(FNc(\mathcal{Q}_N)) \cap FNc(FNi(\mathcal{Q}_N)) \subseteq \mathcal{Q}_N$

We'll utilize shortened versions of $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -Nbhd, for the word $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -neighbourhood

Definition 2.2. Let Γ be an fn ts and let $\mathcal{Q}_n^1 \in \Gamma$. A part of \mathbb{N} of Γ is $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -Nbhd of \mathcal{Q}_n^1 , if \exists a $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -OS, E such that $\mathcal{Q}_n^1 \in E \subset \mathbb{N}$.

Definition 2.3. Let \mathcal{Q}_N be a subset of Γ . Then, if \mathcal{Q}_N is a $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -Nbhd of \mathcal{Q}_n^1 , then $\mathcal{Q}_n^1 \in \mathcal{Q}_N$ is to be $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -point of interior \mathcal{Q}_N . $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -interior \mathcal{Q}_N is the whole set $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -point of interior \mathcal{Q}_N , and it is $b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -int(\mathcal{Q}_N), $IN_{b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}}(\mathcal{Q}_N) = \cup \{E: E \text{ is } FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}OS, E \subset \mathcal{Q}_N\}$

Let be the part of a space $\mathcal{Q}_N \Gamma$. The meeting point for all $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -closed sets containing \mathcal{Q}_N is defined as the $FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -closure of \mathcal{Q}_N , $CL_{b_{\mathcal{Q}_N}}(\mathcal{Q}_N) = \cap \{E: \mathcal{Q}_N \subset E \in FNb_{\mathcal{Q}_N}(\Gamma)\}$

Definition 2.4. An Q_N be a space that has a group of individuals. Γ , an element $q_n^1 \in \Gamma$ is to be b_{Q_N} -point of Q_N if for all b_{Q_N} -OS, Γ_1 containing q_n^1 , $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_N - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. The whole set b_{Q_N} -point of Q_N is b_{Q_N} -derived (briefly. $E_{b_{Q_N}}$) of Q_N as indicated by $E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Example 2.5. Let $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ and $Y = \{0_N, 1_N, Q_{N1}, Q_{N2}, Q_{N3}, Q_{N4}\}$ where
 $Q_{N1} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.82, \Gamma(\alpha)0.79, \Gamma(\alpha)0.59 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.4, \Gamma(\beta)0.61, \Gamma(\beta)0.4 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.39, \Gamma(\gamma)0.4, \Gamma(\gamma)0.5 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N2} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.69, \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.39 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.78, \Gamma(\beta)0.2, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.99, \Gamma(\gamma)0.39, \Gamma(\gamma)0.19 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N3} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.82, \Gamma(\alpha)0.78, \Gamma(\alpha)0.49 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.8, \Gamma(\beta)0.51, \Gamma(\beta)0.4 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.9, \Gamma(\gamma)0.7, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N4} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.69, \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.59 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.59, \Gamma(\beta)0.21, \Gamma(\beta)0.4 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.39, \Gamma(\gamma)0.3, \Gamma(\gamma)0.4 \rangle\}$.
 Here Q_{N3} be a subset of a space Γ and a point $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and Γ_1 a b_{Q_N} -OS, then it is a b_{Q_N} -point of Q_N is $E_{b_{Q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.82, \Gamma(\alpha)0.79, \Gamma(\alpha)0.49 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.8, \Gamma(\beta)0.51, \Gamma(\beta)0.4 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.9, \Gamma(\gamma)0.7, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2 \rangle\})$.

Theorem 2.6. As for segments Q_{N1}, Q_{N2} of a space Γ , all of the following claims are true::

If $Q_{N2} \supset Q_{N1}$, then

- a) $E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N2}) \supset E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$
- b) $E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1} \cup Q_{N2}) \supset E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N2})$
- c) $E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) \supset E_{b_{Q_N}}(E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})) - Q_{N1}$
- d) $Q_{N1} \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) \supset E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1} \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}))$.

Proof. (a) It is obvious. (b) It is an immediate consequence of (c).

(c) If $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})) - Q_{N1}$ and Γ_1 is a b_{Q_N} -OS, offering q_n^1 , $\Gamma_1 \cap (E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. Permit $q_n^2 \in \Gamma_1 \cap (E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) - \{q_n^1\})$. Then due to the fact $q_n^2 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$, $q_n^2 \in \Gamma_1$, $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_{N1} - \{q_n^2\}) \neq \emptyset$. Permit $\Gamma^\# \in \Gamma_1 \cap (Q_{N1} - \{q_n^2\})$, $\Gamma^\# \neq q_n^1$ to be for $\Gamma^\# \in Q_{N1}$, $q_n^1 \notin Q_{N1}$. Accordingly $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_{N1} - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. Consequently $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$.

(d) Let's Take $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$. If $q_n^1 \in Q_N$, The ultimate result is clear. Let $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) - Q_N$, for b_{Q_N} -OS, $\Gamma_1 \subset Q_N^1$, $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. Consequently $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_N - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$ or $\Gamma_1 \cap (E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. It eventually follows (c) that $\Gamma_1 \cap (Q_N - \{q_n^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. So $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$. So, whatever the circumstance, $Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \supset E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$.

Theorem 2.7. In any subset that exists Q_N of a Γ , $b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N) = Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Proof. Since $E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \subset b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N)$, $Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \subset b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N)$. As opposed to that, let $q_n^1 \in b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N)$. If $q_n^1 \in Q_N$, then the evidence is conclusive. If $q_n^1 \notin Q_N$, then every single b_{Q_N} -OS $\Gamma_1 \subset Q_N^1 \cap Q_N$ at something different from q_n^1 . Consequently $q_n^1 \in E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$. Thus $Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \supset b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N) \Rightarrow b_{Q_N}CLof(Q_N) = Q_N \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$. This concludes the evidence to be presented.

Observation 2.8. In any subset that exists Q_{N1}, Q_{N2} of Γ , These statements are all accurate:

- a) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$ being the biggest b_{Q_N} -OS $\subset Q_{N1}$.
- b) Q_{N1} is b_{Q_N} -OS $\Leftrightarrow Q_{N1} = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$.
- c) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1})$.
- d) $\Gamma - CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N1}) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N1})$.

- e) $Q_{N_1} \subset Q_{N_2}$, then $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_2}) \supset IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_1})$.
- f) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}) \supset IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_1}) \cup IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_2})$.

Theorem 2.9. In any of the subsets Q_{N_1}, Q_{N_2} of Γ , All of these claims are true:

- a) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_1}) = Q_{N_1} - E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$.
- b) $\Gamma - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_{N_1}) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$.

Proof.

(a) Let $q_n^1 \in Q_{N_1} - E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) \Rightarrow q_n^1 \notin E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$ and so \exists a b_{Q_N} -OS, Γ_1 containing q_n^1 such that $\Gamma_1 \cap (\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) = \phi$. Then $q_n^1 \in \Gamma_1 \subset Q_{N_1}$ and hence $q_n^1 \in b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1})$, i.e., $Q_{N_1} - E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) \subset b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1})$. As opposed to that, if $q_n^1 \in b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1}) \Rightarrow q_n^1 \notin E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$. Since $b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1})$ is b_{Q_N} -open and $b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1}) \cap (\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) = \phi$. Hence $b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1}) = Q_{N_1} - E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$.

(b) $\Gamma - b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_{N_1}) = \Gamma - (Q_{N_1} - E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})) = (\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_{N_1}) = b_{Q_N}CLof(\Gamma - Q_{N_1})$.

Definition 2.10. In any of the subsets Q_N of Γ , $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Q_N - b_{Q_N}INTof(Q_N)$ It has been stated to have b_{Q_N} -border about Q_N .

Example 2.11. Let $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ and $Y = \{0_N, 1_N, Q_{N_1}, Q_{N_2}, Q_{N_3}, Q_{N_4}\}$ where
 $Q_{N_1} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.71, \Gamma(\alpha)0.69, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.52, \Gamma(\beta)0.43 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N_2} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.61, \Gamma(\alpha)0.36 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.76, \Gamma(\beta)0.23, \Gamma(\beta)0.33 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.89, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N_3} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.62, \Gamma(\alpha)0.68, \Gamma(\alpha)0.39 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.18, \Gamma(\beta)0.61, \Gamma(\beta)0.74 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.19, \Gamma(\gamma)0.23, \Gamma(\gamma)0.43 \rangle\}$,
 $Q_{N_4} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.39, \Gamma(\alpha)0.49, \Gamma(\alpha)0.39 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.62, \Gamma(\beta)0.24, \Gamma(\beta)0.14 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.23, \Gamma(\gamma)0.31, \Gamma(\gamma)0.32 \rangle\}$
 Here Q_{N_2} be a subset of a space Γ and
 $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.61, \Gamma(\alpha)0.36 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.76, \Gamma(\beta)0.23, \Gamma(\beta)0.33 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.89, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29 \rangle\}) =$
 $\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.61, \Gamma(\alpha)0.36 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.76, \Gamma(\beta)0.23, \Gamma(\beta)0.33 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.89, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29 \rangle\} -$
 $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.59, \Gamma(\alpha)0.61, \Gamma(\alpha)0.36 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.76, \Gamma(\beta)0.23, \Gamma(\beta)0.33 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.89, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29, \Gamma(\gamma)0.29 \rangle\})$

Observation 2.12. In any of the subsets Q_N of Γ , All of these claims are true:

- a) $Q_N = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup \beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.
- b) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap \beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = \phi$.
- c) Q_N a b_{Q_N} -OS $\Leftrightarrow \beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = \phi$.
- d) $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = \phi$.
- e) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = \phi$.

Theorem 2.13. In any of the subsets Q_N of Γ , All of these claims are correct:

- a) $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = \beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.
- b) $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Q_N \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N)$.
- c) $\beta d^{#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = E_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N)$.

Proof.

(a) If $q_n^1 \in IN_{b_{q_N}}(\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N))$, then $q_n^1 \in \beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$. As opposed to that, $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \subset q_N$, $q_n^1 \in IN_{b_{q_N}}(\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)) \subset IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$. Hence $q_n^1 \in IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) \cap \beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ which contradicts (c). Thus \cap of $IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ & $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ is ϕ .

(b) $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) =$ difference of $IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ from $q_N = q_N - (\Gamma - CL_{b_{q_N}}(\Gamma - q_N)) = q_N \cap CL_{b_{q_N}}(\Gamma - q_N)$.

(c) $\beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) =$ difference of $IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ from $q_N = q_N - (q_N - \mathfrak{D}\epsilon^{\alpha\delta}(\Gamma - q_N)) = \mathfrak{E}_{b_{q_N}}(\Gamma - q_N)$.

Definition 2.14. A b_{q_N} -frontier of any of the subsets q_N of Γ is $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = \cap$ of $CL_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) \& CL_{b_{q_N}}(\Gamma \setminus q_N)$.

Example 2.15. Let $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ and consider the family $Y = \{0_N, 1_N, q_{N_1}, q_{N_2}\}$ where $q_{N_1} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.6, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.7, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.1, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.6 \rangle\}$, $q_{N_2} = \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.9, \Gamma(\alpha)0.1, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.6, \Gamma(\beta)0.2, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.9, \Gamma(\gamma)0.9, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2 \rangle\}$. Here q_{N_1} be a subset of a space Γ and $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.6, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.7, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.1, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.6 \rangle\})$ is equal to $CL_{b_{q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.6, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.7, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.1, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.6 \rangle\}) \cap CL_{b_{q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.6, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.7, \Gamma(\beta)0.3 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.1, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.6 \rangle\})$.

Theorem 2.16. In any of the subsets q_N of Γ , All of these claims are true:

- a) $CL_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) = IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) \cup Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$
- b) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = \beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \cup \mathfrak{E}_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$.
- c) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = CL_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) \cap CL_{b_{q_N}}(\Gamma \setminus q_N)$.
- d) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$ is b_{q_N} -closed

Theorem 2.17. In any of the subsets q_N of Γ , All of these claims are correct:

- a) $IN_{b_{q_N}}(q_N) \cap Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = \phi$.
- b) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \supset \beta d^{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N)$.
- c) q_N is b_{q_N} -open set iff $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = \mathfrak{E}_{b_{q_N}}(q_N)$
- d) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) = Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(\Gamma \setminus q_N)$
- e) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \supset CL_{b_{q_N}}(Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N))$.
- f) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \supset Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N))$.
- g) $Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(q_N) \supset Fr_{\#b_{q_N}}(CL_{b_{q_N}}(q_N))$

h) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Q_N - Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Proof.

(a) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup (CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

(b) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap (CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = \phi$.

(c) Since $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup \beta d^{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$,
 $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = \beta d^{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup E_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$

(d) $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma \setminus Q_N)$.

(e) $CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}}(X \setminus Q_N))$
 $\subset CL_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma \setminus Q_N)) = Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Hence $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$ is b_{Q_N} -closed.

(f) $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}$ of $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$
 $\subset CL_{b_{Q_N}}$ of $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$

(g) $Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) =$
 $CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

(h) $Q_N - Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = Q_N - (CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Within the ensuing theorem $FNB_{Q_N}^{(C)}$ indicate the group of points q_n^1 of Γ which a function is used $q: (\Gamma_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (\Gamma_2, \xi_2)$ is not FNB_{Q_N} -C.

Theorem 2.18. The $U(FNB_{Q_N})$ -frontiers of the mirror reflections of FNB_{Q_N} -OS that includes $q(q_n^1)$ is \Leftrightarrow to $FNB_{Q_N}^{(C)}$.

Proof. Proceed to consider q is not FNB_{Q_N} -at a point, continuous q_n^1 of $\Gamma_1 \Rightarrow \exists$ an OS, $J \subset \Gamma_2$ containing $q(q_n^1) \mid q(I)$ is not a portion of $J \forall I \in FNB_{Q_N}O(\Gamma_1)$ containing q_n^1 . Hence we've $I \cap (\Gamma_1 - q^{-1}(J)) \neq \phi, \forall I \in FNB_{Q_N}O(\Gamma_1)$ containing q_n^1 . It follows that $q_n^1 \in CL_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma_1 - q^{-1}(Q_N))$. Additionally, we have $q_n^1 \in q^{-1}(J) \subset CL_{b_{Q_N}}(q^{-1}(Q_N))$. Thus, it follows that $q_n^1 \in Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(q^{-1}(J))$. Now, let q be FNB_{Q_N} -Cont. at $q_n^1 \in \Gamma_1$ and $J \subset \Gamma_2$ be any OS containing $q(q_n^1)$. Then $q_n^1 \in q^{-1}(J)$ is a FNB_{Q_N} -open set of Γ_1 . Thus $q_n^1 \in IN_{b_{Q_N}}(q^{-1}(J))$ and therefore $q_n^1 \notin Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(q^{-1}(J))$ for every OS, J containing $q(q_n^1)$.

Definition 2.19. In any of the subsets Q_N of a Γ , $E^{FNB_{Q_N}}$ of Q_N is b_{Q_N} INT of $\Gamma - Q_N$ this will eventually take place. FNB_{Q_N} -exterior regarding Q_N .

Example 2.20. Let $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ and consider the family $Y = \{0_N, 1_N, Q_{N_1}, Q_{N_2}\}$ where
 $Q_{N_1} = \{(\Gamma(\alpha)0.4, \Gamma(\alpha)0.5, \Gamma(\alpha)0.4), (\Gamma(\beta)0.6, \Gamma(\beta)0.6, \Gamma(\beta)0.4), (\Gamma(\gamma)0.3, \Gamma(\gamma)0.4, \Gamma(\gamma)0.7)\}$,
 $Q_{N_2} = \{(\Gamma(\alpha)0.8, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3, \Gamma(\alpha)0.2), (\Gamma(\beta)0.4, \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.2), (\Gamma(\gamma)0.3, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.3)\}$,

Here Q_{N_1} be a subset of a space Γ and

$$E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.8, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3, \Gamma(\alpha)0.2 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.4, \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.2 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.3, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.3 \rangle\}) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - \{\langle \Gamma(\alpha)0.8, \Gamma(\alpha)0.3, \Gamma(\alpha)0.2 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\beta)0.4, \Gamma(\beta)0.3, \Gamma(\beta)0.2 \rangle, \langle \Gamma(\gamma)0.3, \Gamma(\gamma)0.2, \Gamma(\gamma)0.3 \rangle\}).$$

Observation 2.21. In any of the subsets Q_N of Γ , All of these claims are true:

- a) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$ is FNb_{Q_N} -OS.
- b) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N) = \Gamma - CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.
- c) If $Q_N^1 \subset Q_N^2 \Rightarrow E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N^1) \supset E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N^2)$.
- d) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N^1 \cup Q_N^2) \subset E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N^1) \cup E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N^2)$.
- e) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\Gamma) = \phi$.
- f) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\phi) = \Gamma$.
- g) $\Gamma = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \cup Fr_{\#b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.

Theorem 2.22. In any of the subsets Q_N of Γ , All of these claims are correct:

- a) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$.
- b) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N) = E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$.
- c) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \subset E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$.

Proof.

- (a) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$
 $= IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - (\Gamma - CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$.
- (b) $E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N))$
 $= IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - (\Gamma - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N))) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N)) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N) = E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$.
- (c) $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N) \subset IN_{b_{Q_N}}(CL_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - Q_N))$
 $= IN_{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma - E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N)) = E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(E^{FNb_{Q_N}}(Q_N))$

Definition 2.23. Γ be an *fnts* and let $q_n^1 \in \Gamma$. A subset N of Γ is *fn-b_{Q_N}-Nbhd* of q_n^1 , if \exists a *fn-b_{Q_N}-OS*, $E \mid q_n^1 \in E \subset N$.

Definition 2.24. An Q_N be a $\subset \Gamma$, $q_n^1 \in Q_N$ meant to be *fn-b_{Q_N}-innermost point* Q_N if Q_N is a *fn-b_{Q_N}-Nbhd* of q_n^1 . The entire set *fn-b_{Q_N}-point of interior* Q_N is *fn-b_{Q_N}-interior* Q_N and it is $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$, $IN_{b_{Q_N}}(Q_N)$ is union of $\{L: L \text{ is } fnb_{Q_N} \text{ OS, } L \subset Q_N\}$

A \mathcal{Q}_N be a section of a space. Γ We define $\text{FNb}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -closure of \mathcal{Q}_N to serve as a junction for all $\text{FNb}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -closed sets made of \mathcal{Q}_N , $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ CL of $\mathcal{Q}_N = \bigcap \{L: \mathcal{Q}_N \subset L \in \text{fnb}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}(\Gamma)\}$

Definition 2.25. \mathcal{Q}_N an area where a number of elements are present. Γ , an element $\mathcal{Q}_N^1 \in \Gamma$ is to be $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -point of \mathcal{Q}_N if $\forall \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -OS, Γ_1 containing \mathcal{Q}_N^1 , $\Gamma_1 \cap (\mathcal{Q}_N - \{\mathcal{Q}_N^1\}) \neq \emptyset$. The whole set $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -point of \mathcal{Q}_N is $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -derived (briefly, $\mathcal{E}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}}$) a bunch of \mathcal{Q}_N as indicated by $\mathcal{E}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}}(\mathcal{Q}_N)$.

Definition 2.26. In any subset $\exists \mathcal{Q}_N$ of a Γ , $\mathcal{E}^{\text{FNb}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}}(\mathcal{Q}_N)$ is $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ Int of $\Gamma - \mathcal{Q}_N$ this will occur $\text{FNb}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}$ -exterior regarding \mathcal{Q}_N .

Definition 2.27. Let (F, Γ_F) be an FNTS. Two never empty FNS's \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} of Γ are regarded as Γ^S -segregated if $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \emptyset$, $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \emptyset$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} = \emptyset$. Both of these circumstances are comparable to the one condition. $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2})) \cup (\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \emptyset$.

Definition 2.28. Let a FNTS be (F, Γ_F) . If G is a FN subset of F , then the collection Γ^S of G is $\{G \cap U: U \in \Gamma\}$ G is referred to be a FN subspace topology on F if is a FNT on G .

Observation 2.29. FN disjoint is any two FN separated sets. FN, however, does not necessarily divide two independent sets of FN.

Theorem 2.30. A $(G, \Gamma^S(G))$ be a FNTS's FN subspace. (F, Γ_F) , $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}, \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}$ be 2 NF sets of G . Then $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}, \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}$ a FN Γ^S -segregated \Leftrightarrow they are FN $\Gamma^S(G)$ -segregated.

Proof: By concept, $\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) = \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap G$ and $\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cap G$.

$$\text{Now } (\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cup (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2})) = (\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap G \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cup (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cap G) = (\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cup (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2})).$$

$$\text{Hence } (\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cup (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} G(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2})) = \emptyset$$

$$\Leftrightarrow (\text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cup (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{CL}_{\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N}} F(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2})) = \emptyset, \text{ because } \mathcal{Q}_{N_1}, \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} \subset G.$$

It follows that $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}, \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}$ are FN Γ^S -segregated if and only if they are FN $\Gamma^S(G)$ -segregated.

Theorem 2.31. If \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} are Γ^S -segregated sets of an FNTS (F, Γ_F) and $C_1 \subset \mathcal{Q}_{N_1}$ and $C_2 \subset \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}$, then C_1 and C_2 are also $\Gamma^S(G)$ -segregated.

Proof: Given $C_1 \subset \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \Rightarrow \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(C_1) \subset \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of (\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) and $C_2 \subset \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} \Rightarrow \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(C_2) \subset \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of (\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) . Since $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \emptyset$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} = \emptyset$. It follows that $C_1 \cap \text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(C_2) = \emptyset$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(C_1) \cap C_2 = \emptyset$. Hence C_1 and C_2 are $\Gamma^S(G)$ -segregated.

Theorem 2.32. Two FNC(FNO) sets \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} of an FNTS are Γ^S -segregated \Leftrightarrow They don't make appropriate.

Proof: Given that any 2 Γ^S -segregated sets don't match. If \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} are both disjoint and FN closed, then $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1} \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} = \emptyset$, $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) = \mathcal{Q}_{N_1}$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) = \mathcal{Q}_{N_2}$. So $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} = \emptyset$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}) \cap \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} = \emptyset$ implies \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} are Γ^S -segregated. If \mathcal{Q}_{N_1} and \mathcal{Q}_{N_2} are both disjoint and FN open, then $\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}(c)$ and $\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}(c)$ are both FN closed so that $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_1}(c))$ and $\text{b}_{\mathcal{Q}_N} CL$ of $(\mathcal{Q}_{N_2}(c))$.

Also $Q_{N_1} \cap Q_{N_2} = \phi_N \Rightarrow Q_{N_1} \subset Q_{N_2}(c)$ and $Q_{N_2} \subset Q_{N_1}(c) \Rightarrow b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_1}) \subset b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_2}(c)) = Q_{N_2}(c)$ and $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_2}) \subset b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_1}(c)) = Q_{N_1}(c) \Rightarrow b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2} = \phi_N$ and $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(Q_{N_2}) \cap Q_{N_1} = \phi_N \Rightarrow Q_{N_1}$ and Q_{N_2} are Γ^S -segregated.

Theorem 2.33. Two FN disjoint sets Q_{N_1} and Q_{N_2} are Γ^S -segregated in an FNTS $(F, \Gamma_F) \Leftrightarrow$ they are both FNO & FNC in the FN subspace $Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}$.

Proof: Let the disjoint FN sets Q_{N_1} and Q_{N_2} be Γ^S -segregated in Γ , so that $Q_{N_1} \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_2}) = \phi_N$ and $Q_{N_2} \cap CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) = \phi_N$. Let $L = Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}$, $CL_{b_{Q_N}} L(Q_{N_1}) = CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap L = CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap (Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}) = [CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_1}] \cup [CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2}] = Q_{N_1} \cup \phi_N = Q_{N_1}$ [because $Q_{N_1} \subset CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1})$ and $CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2} = \phi_N$]. A is FNC in the FN subspace $Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}$, by the definition of FNC. Similarly Q_{N_2} is FNC in $Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}$. Again $Q_{N_1} \cap Q_{N_2} = \phi_N$, they are complements of each other in L and hence they are both FNO in L . Conversely, let the disjoint FN sets Q_{N_1} and Q_{N_2} be both FNO and FNC in L . So $Q_{N_1} = b_{Q_N} CL$ of $L(Q_{N_1}) = [b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap L] = b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap (Q_{N_1} \cup Q_{N_2}) = [b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_1}] \cup [b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2}] = Q_{N_1} \cup [b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2}]$ because $Q_{N_1} \subset b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \rightarrow (1)$. Since $Q_{N_1} \cap Q_{N_2} = \phi_N \Rightarrow Q_{N_1} \cap (b_{Q_N} CL$ of $\Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2}) = \phi_N$, it follows from (1) that is $(CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_1}) \cap Q_{N_2}) = \phi_N$. Similarly $(CL_{b_{Q_N}} \Gamma(Q_{N_2}) \cap Q_{N_1}) = \phi_N$. Hence Q_{N_1} and Q_{N_2} are Γ^S -segregated in Γ .

Definition 2.34. Let Γ be a FNTS. A set $Y \subset \Gamma$ is said to be b_{Q_N} -Sat if for every $\gamma \in Y$ it follows $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma\}) \subset Y$. The grouping of all b_{Q_N} -saturated sets in Γ , we indicate by $Sat^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$.

Theorem 2.35. Let Γ , a FNTS. Then $\delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$ is a whole algebraic Boolean set.

Proof. We'll demonstrate that every combination and complement of each element in $\delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$ are members of $\delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$. Of course, the only proof that is not trivial is the one using the complements. Let $Y \in \delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$ and suppose that $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma_1\})$ does not contained in $\Gamma - Y$ for some $\gamma_1 \in \Gamma - Y$. Then there exists $\gamma_2 \in Y$ such that $\gamma_2 \in b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma_1\})$. It follows that γ_1, γ_2 possess no disjoint neighbourhoods. Then $\gamma_1 \in b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma_2\})$. However, this is in conflict with the notion of $\delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$ we have $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma_2\}) \subset Y$. Hence, $b_{Q_N} CL$ of $(\{\gamma_1\}) \subset \Gamma - Y$ for every $\gamma_1 \in \Gamma - Y$, which implies $\Gamma - Y \in \delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$.

Corollary 2.36. $\delta^{b_{Q_N}}(\Gamma)$ includes each intersection and union of b_{Q_N} -CS and b_{Q_N} -OS's in Γ .

Definition 2.37. A function $\alpha: (\Gamma_1, Q_1) \rightarrow (\Gamma_2, Q_2)$ is referred to as

- a) $b_{Q_N}(C\#)$ if $\alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$ is b_{Q_N} -CS in (Γ_1, Q_1) for every CS Q_2 of (Γ_2, Q_2) .
- b) b_{Q_N} -Totally-Continuous (briefly. $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{Q_N}} \rangle C$) at a point $\gamma_1 \in \Gamma_1$ if for each open subset Q_2 in Γ_2 containing $\alpha(\gamma_1)$, there exists a b_{Q_N} -clopen subset Q_1 in Γ_1 containing γ_1 such that $\alpha(Q_1) \subset Q_2$
- c) $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{Q_N}} \rangle C$ if it has this property at each point of Γ_1 .

Theorem 2.38. The following statements are equivalent for a function $\alpha: (\Gamma_1, Q_1) \rightarrow (\Gamma_2, Q_2)$:

- a) α is $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$;
- b) $\forall OS, Q_2$ of Γ_2 , $\alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$ is $b_{eN}CLOS$ in Γ_1 ;

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b) Let Q_2 be an OS of a Γ_2 and let $\gamma \in \alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$. Since $(\gamma) \in Q_2$, by (a), \exists a b_{eN} -CLOS $Q_{1,\gamma}$ in Γ_1 containing γ such that $Q_{1,\gamma} \subset \alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$. We obtain $\alpha^{-1}(Q_2) = \cup_{\gamma \in \alpha^{-1}(Q_2)} Q_{1,\gamma}$. Thus, $\alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$ is b_{eN} -CLOS in Γ_1 .

(b) \Rightarrow (a) Clear.

Remark 2.39. Every $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C \Rightarrow b_{eN}(C\#)$.

Definition 2.40. A space $(\Gamma_1, \mathcal{Q}_1)$ is said to be $b_{eN} < \sim S >$ if every b_{eN} -OS of Q_1 is OS in Q_1 .

Remark 2.41. If a function $\alpha: (\Gamma_1, \mathcal{Q}_1) \rightarrow (\Gamma_2, \mathcal{Q}_2)$ is totally continuous and Q_1 is a $b_{eN} < \sim S >$, then α is $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$.

Definition 2.42. An FNTS $(\Gamma_1, \mathcal{Q}_1)$ is said to be $b_{eN} \ll \mathcal{C} \circ n$ if the combination of two nonempty disjoint b_{eN} -OS cannot be expressed in writing.

Theorem 2.43. If α is a $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$ -function from a $b_{eN} \ll \mathcal{C} \circ n$ -space Q_1 onto any space Q_2 , then Q_2 is an indiscrete space.

Proof. If possible, suppose that Q_2 is not indiscrete. Let L be a valid OS of Γ_2 that isn't empty. Then $\alpha^{-1}(L)$ is a valid non-empty b_{eN} -CLOS of $(\Gamma_1, \mathcal{Q}_1)$, it is a contradiction to the fact that Γ_1 is $b_{eN} \ll \mathcal{C} \circ n$ -space.

Theorem 2.44. The set of all points $\gamma \in X$ wherein a function $\alpha: (\Gamma_1, \mathcal{Q}_1) \rightarrow (\Gamma_2, \mathcal{Q}_2)$ is not $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$ is the \cup of $Fr_{\#b_{eN}}$ of the open sets' inverted images that include $\alpha(\gamma)$.

Proof. Suppose that α is not $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$ at $\gamma \in Q_1 \Rightarrow \exists$ an OS Q_2 of Γ_2 containing $\alpha(\gamma)$ such that $\alpha(Q_1)$ is not contained in Q_2 for each $Q_1 \in b_{eN}O(\Gamma_1)$ containing γ and hence $\gamma \in b_{eN}CL$ of $(\Gamma_1 \setminus \alpha^{-1}(Q_2))$. On the other hand, $\Gamma_1 \in \alpha^{-1}(Q_2) \subset b_{eN}CL$ of $(f^{-1}(Q_2))$ and hence $\Gamma_1 \in Fr_{\#b_{eN}}(\alpha^{-1}(Q_2))$.

Conversely, suppose that α is $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$ at $\gamma \in \Gamma_1$ and let Q_2 be an OS of Γ_2 containing $\alpha(\gamma) \Rightarrow \exists Q_1 \in b_{eN}O(\Gamma_1)$ containing γ such that $Q_1 \subset \alpha^{-1}(Q_2)$. Hence $\gamma \in b_{eN}INT$ of $(\alpha^{-1}(Q_2))$. Therefore, $\Gamma_1 \in Fr_{\#b_{eN}}(\alpha^{-1}(Q_2))$ for each open set Q_2 of Γ_2 containing $\alpha(\gamma)$.

Conclusion: We have given an introduction to fn - $Fr_{\#b_{eN}}$, including the ideas of closed and open sets. We examined features in fn - $\beta d^{\#b_{eN}}$ and fn - $E_{b_{eN}}(\mathcal{Q}_N)$, and we evaluated some of their features in fn -topological spaces to provide an idea of the findings we gained by adding the concept of fn - b_{eN} OS. We have produced a comparisons between the provided concepts of border, exterior, and derived. Additionally, we studied and identified the features of $\langle \mathcal{J}^{b_{eN}} \rangle C$ -functions and Γ^S -

segregated functions. In the future, we want to investigate more findings derived from the aforementioned principles and endeavour to provide applications.

References

1. Ali Hussein Mahmood Al-Obaidi, Qays Hatem Imran, and Murtadha Mohammed Abdulkadhim, On New Types of Weakly Neutrosophic Crisp Closed Functions, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2022**, Volume 50, pp. 239-247. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6774789.
2. Alkan Özkan, Şeyda Yazgan and Sandeep Kaur, Neutrosophic Soft Generalized b-Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Soft Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 56, pp. 48-69. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8194715.
3. P.Anbarasi Rodrigo and S.Maheswari Neutrosophic $gs\alpha^*$ -Open and Closed Maps in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications*, **2023**, Volume 8, pp. 42-49. <https://doi.org/10.61356/j.nswa.2023.39>.
4. Arockiarani I, Martina Jency J, More on Fuzzy Neutrosophic Sets and Fuzzy Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *IJIRS* **2014**, Volume 3, pp. 642:652.
5. Basker P, Broumi Said. $N\psi_{\alpha}^{\# 0}$ and $N\psi_{\alpha}^{\# 1}$ -spaces in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, **2021**, Volume 16, pp. 09-15.
6. Basker P, Broumi Said, On Neutrosophic Homeomorphisms in Neutrosophic Functions, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 55, pp. 403-414.
7. Basker P.; Broumi Said. On (β_{pn}) -OS in Pythagorean Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, **2022**, Volume 18, No.4, 183-191.
8. Fatimah M. Mohammed, Anas A Hijab, Shaymaa F Matar. Fuzzy Neutrosophic Weakly-Generalized Closed Sets in Fuzzy Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *Journal of University of Anbar for Pure Science*, **2018**, Volume 12, pp. 63-72.
9. Florentin Smarandache. Definition of Neutrosophic Logic-A Generalization of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Logic, *Proceedings of the Third Conference of the European Society for Fuzzy Logic and Technology*, **2003**, EUSFLAT, pp. 10-12.
10. Florentin Smarandache, New Types of Topologies and Neutrosophic Topologies (Improved Version), *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 57, pp. 234-244. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8271368.
11. Gayathri N and Helen M, Some Characterizations of Linguistic Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 58, pp. 432-442. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8404506.
12. Huda E Khalid, Ramiz Sabbagh, Ahmed A Salma, Thanoon Y Thanoon, Elagamy H A, Novel Neutrosophic Objects Within Neutrosophic Topology $(N(X),\tau)$, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 62, pp. 342-350, 2023. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/10436916>.
13. Huda E Khalid, Ramiz Sabbagh, Ahmed A Salma, Thanoon Y Thanoon, Elagamy H A, Novel Neutrosophic Objects Within Neutrosophic Topology, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 61, pp. 260-274. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10428622
14. Krassimir Atanassov. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, **1986**, Volume 20, pp. 87-96.
15. Krassimir T. Atanassov. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets, *Physica-Verlag, Heidelberg N Y*, **1999**.
16. Krassimir Atanassov. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, VII ITKR's Session, Sofia, June 1983 (Deposited in Central Sci. - Techn. Library of Bulg. Acad. of Sci., 1697/84) (in Bulgarian); Reprinted, *Int. J Bioautomation*, **2016**, Volume 20, pp. S1-S6.
17. Kungumaraj E, Durgadevi S and Tharani N P, Heptagonal Neutrosophic Topology, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 60, pp. 335-356. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10224216.
18. J J Mershia Rabuni and N. Balamani, Computation of Neutrosophic Soft Topology using Python, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 60, pp. 548-569. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10224263.
19. Mohammed Abu-Saleem, Omar almallah and Nizar Kh. Al Ouashouh, An application of neutrosophic theory on manifolds and their topological transformations, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 58, pp. 464-474. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8404512.

20. Muthumari G and Narmada Devi R, Homomorphism and Isomorphism of Neutrosophic Over Topologized Graphs, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 53, pp. 519-529. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7536082.
21. Reena C, Yaamini K S, A New Notion of Neighbourhood and Continuity in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 60, pp. 74-88. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10224128.
22. Sagvan Y Musa, Baravan A Asaad, Connectedness on Hypersoft Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2022, Volume 51, pp. 666-680. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7135399.
23. Salama A A, Alblowi S A, Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *IOSR Journal of Mathematics*, **2012**, Volume 3, pp. 31:35.
24. Smaradache F, Neutrosophic Set: A Generalization of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set, *Journal of Defense Resources Management*, **2010**, Volume 1, pp. 1-10.
25. Sudeep Deyand Gautam Chandra Ray, Separation Axioms in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications*, **2023**, Volume 2, pp. 38-54.
26. Surekha S S and Sindhu G, A Contemporary approach on Generalized NB Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Binary Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 56, pp. 338-350. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8194825.
27. Tomasz Witczak, Interior and closure in anti-minimal and anti-biminimal spaces in the frame of anti-topology, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 56, pp. 429-440. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8194845.
28. Thangaraja P, Vadivel A and John Sundar C, e-Open Maps, e-Closed Maps and e-Homeomorphisms in N-Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **2023**, Volume 60, pp. 287-299. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10224202.
29. Zadeh L A, Fuzzy sets, *Information and Control*, **1965**, Volume 8, pp. 338-353.

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